

that the benzimidazole NH is not involved in coordination.

References

1. P. C. H. MITCHELL, *Quart. Rev.*, 1966, 20, 99.
2. T. A. GEORG and C. D. SEIBOLD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 6859.
3. H. K. SAHA and M. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 3719.
4. H. K. SAHA and A. K. BANERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 2989; 1972, 34, 697, 1861.
5. A. KAY and P. C. H. MITCHELL, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1970, 2421; 1973, 1388.
6. M. N. MAJUMDAR and A. M. SAHA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, 38, 1374.
7. R. F. WEINLAND and M. FIEDERER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2090, and references therein.
8. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 7, 545.
9. H. B. GRAY and C. H. HARE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 363.
10. S. P. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARJEE and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 308.
11. T. J. LANE, I. NAKAGAWA, J. L. WALTER and A. K. KANDATHIL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 267.
12. B. C. CURRAN, D. N. SEN, S. MUZUSHIMA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 429.

**Thermodynamic Study of Complexation of
2-Hydroxy- and 2,4-Dihydroxy-deoxybenzoins
with Iron(III), Copper(II), Zinc(II)
and Cadmium(II)**

N. PRIYOKUMAR** and N. R. BANNERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi,
Delhi-110 007

*Manuscript received 16 April 1987, revised 6 June 1989,
accepted 21 June 1989*

THE present paper describes a thermodynamic study on the complexation of 2-hydroxydeoxybenzoin (2-HDB) and 2,4-dihydroxydeoxybenzoin (2,4-DHDB) with Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}. Stability constants were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum's titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of extra pure (E. Merck) or A.R. grade. The ligands 2-HDB and 2,4-DHDB were prepared and purified by standard procedures^{2,3}. Equilibrium studies were conducted (298 K) at four different ionic strengths (NaClO₄) 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 mol dm⁻³ and those for the 2-HDB system (293 and 303 K) and for the 2,4-DHDB system (303 and 308 K) were conducted at an ionic strength of 0.10 dm⁻³. Dioxane-water (1:1, v/v) was used as solvent for the 2-HDB systems and ethanol-water (1:1, v/v) for the 2,4-

DHDB systems, and solvent corrections⁴ were made. Temperature was maintained within ± 0.02 K in a MLW (West Germany) NBE type thermostat. The pH measurements were made with a Radiometer PHM 26 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.005 pH-unit).

Results and Discussion

Titration of only one of the two ionisable protons in 2,4-DHDB could be observed at the given experimental conditions. The pH range of complexation with Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were 2.5–3.1, 4.2–6.3, 5.1–6.6 and 6.7–8.4 for 2-HDB and 2.5–3.4, 4.2–6.4, 5.5–7.5 and 6.5–8.4 for 2,4-DHDB respectively.

The $\bar{n}_H$ values lay between zero and one. Beyond the upper pH limits given above, wide divergence from the normal titration curves occurred due to partial hydrolysis of the complexes. Calculations of $\bar{n}$ and pL were, therefore, done upto the upper pH limits only. The values of $\bar{n}$ before hydrolysis set in, lay between zero and one and as a consequence only the 1:1 metal–ligand complexes have been reported. The experiments were repeated for two different metal–ligand molar ratios and the results were found to be similar which proved the non-formation of polynuclear complexes.

The log K_H and log K values at different ionic strengths⁵ are reported in Table 1. Table 2 incorporates the log K_H and log K values at different temperatures at 0.10 M (NaClO₄) and other thermodynamic parameters. Stabilities of the complexes are

TABLE 1—log K_H AND log K VALUES* OF 2-HYDROXY- AND 2,4-DIHYDROXYDEOXYBENZOIN COMPLEXES** AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTH (I)

Ligand	Cations	log K_H /log K				
		$I = 0.05$	0.1	0.15	0.20	0.00
2-HDB	H	11.84	11.76	11.65	11.63	12.07
	Fe ^{III}	11.88	11.74	11.56	11.52	12.26
	Cu ^{II}	9.15	8.95	8.81	8.68	9.61
	Zn ^{II}	8.10	7.93	7.79	7.68	8.54
	Cd ^{II}	6.56	6.42	6.34	6.21	6.88
2,4-DHDB	H	8.16	8.14	8.13	8.12	8.20
	Fe ^{III}	8.03	7.90	7.80	7.73	8.35
	Cu ^{II}	5.27	5.15	5.03	4.94	5.60
	Zn ^{II}	3.78	3.61	3.53	3.42	4.20
	Cd ^{II}	3.35	3.23	3.14	3.10	3.60

*Limits of error = ± 0.01 – 0.03 in log scale. **At 298 K.

found to decrease with the increasing ionic strength. The thermodynamic stability constants (log K_o) (Table 1) have been obtained by extrapolation of log K vs $\sqrt{I}$ plots to zero ionic strength. The order, Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} of stabilities is in agreement with that of Irving and Williams⁶ and Mellor and Maley⁷. Negative values of free energy (ΔG) indicate that the formation of these complexes

**Department of Chemistry, D. M. College of Science, Imphal, Manipur-795 001.